

Basins of Fixed Points for Composition of the Lotka–Volterra Mappings

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Abstract: The paper considers the composition of two Lotka–Volterra mappings acting in hyperplane H_1 . The basins of the attracting fixed points of the composition are found by using the graphical analysis methods. And also by developing of computer programs, the basins of attractors are clearly shown. The study of the composition of these mappings is important in genetic problems, since genetic problems are suitable in the modeling epidemiological situations. The model proposed in the paper is applicable to study the dynamics of viral diseases transmitted by direct contact in patients who have concomitant diseases. In other words, it can be used to study the course of coexistence of two or more diseases that coincide in time or are pathogenetically interconnected in one patient.

Keywords: Lotka–Volterra mapping, simplex, trajectory, attractor, repeller, the basins of the attractor.

1. INTRODUCTION

Discrete dynamical systems related to the study of the dynamical properties of Lotka–Volterra mappings, which are a special case of general genetic systems describing the evolution of probability distributions of such systems on a simplex. Numerous works are devoted to the study of genetic systems (see, for examples [1–3]).

In present paper, we consider the composition of Lotka–Volterra mappings, which are obviously homeomorphic mappings of the probability distribution space into themselves. The relevance of choosing this problem is dictated by the fact that, unlike the models *SIR*, *SEIR*, *MSIR*, *MSEIR* [4–7], we consider a discrete variant of such systems that more adequately describe the real evolution.

Significant features of nonlinearity are already evident in the study of quadratic transformations, which are also important in applied problems. The study of quadratic transformations of a finitedimensional simplex was started in the works of G.H. Hardy, S.N. Bernstein, E. Fermi, J. Pasta, S. Ulam, G. Kesten, Yu.I. Lubich, and others.

2. PRELIMINARY INFORMATION

Let $H_p = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^m : \sum_{i=1}^m x_i = p\}$ be a hyperplane, and also consider a standard simplex

$$S^{m-1} = \left\{ x \in \mathbb{R}^m : x_i \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^m x_i = 1 \right\} \subset H_1$$

The mapping V of Lotka–Volterra can always be represented as [8–10]

$$x_k^{(n+1)} = x_k^{(n)} \left(1 + \sum_{i=1}^m a_{ki} x_i^{(n)} \right), \quad k = \overline{1, m}. \tag{1}$$

The coefficients of this system satisfy the conditions

$$a_{ki} = -a_{ik}, \quad |a_{ki}| \leq 1. \tag{2}$$

It is easy to notice that the mapping (1) leaves the hyperplane H_1 in itself invariant and the simplex S^{m-1} is basic.

In this paper, we consider the dynamics of the trajectories of the composition of two Lotka–Volterra mappings on the affine shell of a two-dimensional simplex with two mutually inverse tournaments. In studying the dynamics of the Lotka–Volterra mappings, to apply the concept of the tournament is useful [9, 10].

Let $x^0 \in H_1$, then the sequence $\{x^{(n)}\} \subset H_1$, defined by the recurrent formula $x^{(n+1)} = V x^{(n)}$, $n = 0, 1, \dots$ is called a trajectory starting from the point x^0 .

Through $\omega(x^0) = \{x^0, x^{(1)}, \dots\}'$ let's denote the set of limit points of a given trajectory. Obviously, $\omega(x^0)$ is a nonempty closed and invariant subset of H_1 , i.e., there holds $V(\omega(x^0)) \subset \omega(x^0)$.

Let $X = \{x \in H_1 : V x = x\}$ be the set of fixed points of the mapping (1). Note, $V : H_1 \rightarrow H_1$ is continuous, and H_1 convex compact because Julia set for V is compact [11, 12]. Therefore, the set of fixed points of the V mapping is nonempty.

We introduce definitions of the nature of fixed points.

Definition 1. Let $P(x)$ be a mapping on X and let p be a fixed point $P(p) = p$. If all points sufficiently close to p are attracted to p , then this fixed point is called a attracting fixed point. More precisely, if there is an $\varepsilon > 0$ such that for all x in the epsilon neighborhood $N_\varepsilon(p)$ of fixed point is true $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} f^k(x) = p$, then p is attractor.

Definition 2. Let $P(x)$ be a mapping on X and let p be a fixed point $P(p) = p$. If all points sufficiently close to p are repelled from p , then p is called a repelling fixed point. More precisely, if there is an $\varepsilon > 0$ such that for all x in the epsilon neighborhood $N_\varepsilon(p)$ of fixed point is true $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} f^k(x) = p$, then p is called $k \rightarrow \infty$ repeller.

Definition 3. Let $P(x)$ be a mapping on X and let p be an attracting fixed point $P(p) = p$. The set of initial positions of all points, which tends to this fixed point p , is called basin of attractor.

3. THE BASINS OF ATTRACTORS OF LOTKA–VOLTERRA MAPPING COMPOSITIONS

We investigate the Lotka–Volterra mappings of the form (1), which for $m = 3$ maps the hyperplane

$$H_1 = \left\{ x \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i = 1 \right\}$$

to itself, having the following form $a_{ki} = \pm 1$) (with coefficients

$$\begin{cases} x'_1 = x_1(1 + x_2 - x_3) \\ x'_2 = x_2(1 - x_1 - x_3), \\ x'_3 = x_3(1 + x_1 + x_2), \end{cases} \quad , \quad \begin{cases} x'_1 = x_1(1 - x_2 + x_3) \\ x'_2 = x_2(1 + x_1 + x_3), \\ x'_3 = x_3(1 - x_1 - x_2). \end{cases}$$

3

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Fig. 1. Inverse transitive tournaments.

Tournaments corresponding to these mappings $V_1 : S^2 \rightarrow S^2$ and $V_2 : S^2 \rightarrow S^2$ are mutually inverse transitive tournaments [10] (Fig. 1).

Consider the composition of these two mappings $V = V_1 \circ V_2$. Given $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 = 1$, the composition will have the form

$$(3) \quad V : \begin{cases} x'_1 = 1 - x_2^2(2 - x_2) - x_3^2(2 - x_3^2) \\ x'_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2, \\ x'_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3^2). \end{cases}$$

From (2) it can be seen that the last two components of the mapping depend only on themselves. So, we will study the dynamics of these two components separately, as one-dimensional dynamics [11–13]. Later we take the Cartesian product of x_2 and x_3 . Hence, the study of the dynamics of the composition V is equivalent to the study of the dynamics of the projection on the plane x_2Ox_3 , i.e., following twodimensional W mapping

$$(4) \quad W : \begin{cases} x'_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2 \\ x'_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3^2). \end{cases}$$

Now let's study each function separately from (3). 1) Let's start with the function $x'_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2$. To find the fixed points of this W mapping, we solve the equation $x_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2$:

$$x_2 = 0, \quad x_2 = 1, \quad x_2 = \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_2 = \frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}. \tag{5}$$

Let's introduce the notation $f_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2$. Then, we have $f'_2 = 4x_2(x_2 - 2)(x_2 - 1)$.

Consider the characters of fixed points (4)

$$|f'_2(0)| = 0 < 1, \quad |f'_2(1)| = 0 < 1, \quad \left| f'_2\left(\frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \right| \approx 1.52786 > 1$$

$$\left| f'_2\left(\frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \right| \approx 10.4721 > 1.$$

From (3) it is obviously to understand that the fixed points $x_2 = 0, x_2 = 1$ are attractors, and the points $x_2 = \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, x_2 = \frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}$ are repellers.

Next, let's find the basin of attracting fixed points. To do this, by the help of the Koenings-Lamerey diagram [11, 12] we will build graphs of functions and $g(x_2) = x_2$ on one coordinate plane (see Fig. 2).

In Fig. 3, is considered the trajectories of two points $\omega(1,5) = \{1\}$ and $\omega(1,8) = \{0\}$.

The repeller fixed point $x_2 = \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}$ divides the basins of attracting fixed points. At distance ε from the right of this point, the trajectory tends to the point $x_2 = 1$. At the distance ε to the left of this point, the trajectory tends to the point $x_2 = 0$.

Now we will look for almost fixed points for the point $x_2 = \frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}$. These are points, which trajectories after one step fall on the point $x_2 = \frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}$. The coordinates of almost fixed points are the boundary points

Fig. 2. Fixed points.

Fig. 3. Cobweb for two points.

of the basins of a given point. In Fig. 3, we draw a horizontal $f_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2$ line on the abscissa $x_2 = \frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}$ (intersection of graphs for two functions). This line will intersect the graph of the function at four points (see Fig. 4)

$$a = \frac{2 - \sqrt{2(1 + \sqrt{5})}}{2}, \quad b = \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad c = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad d = \frac{2 + \sqrt{2(1 + \sqrt{5})}}{2}.$$

Among the points from (4), the fixed point is the point d . The trajectories of the points a, b, c return to this point d after one step. This means that the points a, b, c are almost attractive. The graphical method states that all points of the interval (a, b) belong to the basin $B(0)$ of the point $x_2 = 0$, i.e., $(a, b) \subset B(0)$. And the intervals (b, c) belong to the fixed point basin $B(1)$ of $x_2 = 1$, i.e., $(b, c) \subset B(1)$. All points of the interval (c, d) in one step will move to the interval (a, b) , hence it follows that the fixed point basin $x_2 = 0$ is the set $(a, b) \cup (c, d) \subset B(0)$.

Now draw a horizontal line through the point $x_2 = 1$. This line will intersect the graph of the function $f_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2$ at two points (see Fig. 5): $a_1 = 1 - \sqrt{2}$, $d_1 = 1 + \sqrt{2}$.

We have obtained the intervals (a_1, a) and (d, d_1) symmetric with respect to the point $x_2 = 1$ and their lengths are equal to one. All trajectories of points from these intervals in one step will fall into the interval (b, c) , i.e., $(a_1, a) \cup (b, c) \cup (d, d_1) \subset B(1)$. Now, for clarity, visually divide the basins (see Fig. 6).

In this Figure we divide a quadrilateral bounded by $\left[\frac{1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right] \times \left[\frac{1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right]$ into two colors: black separates the trajectories of points tending to a fixed point $x_2 = 1$, and light grey separates the points tending to the point $x_2 = 0$.

So, the basins of these points have the following form

$$\left(1 - \sqrt{2}, \frac{2 - \sqrt{2(1 + \sqrt{5})}}{2}\right) \cup \left(\frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \cup \left(\frac{2 + \sqrt{2(1 + \sqrt{5})}}{2}, 1 + \sqrt{2}\right) \subset B(1)$$

Fig. 4. Basins of attractors.

Fig. 5. Inverse graphical analysis.

$$\left(\frac{2 - \sqrt{2(1 + \sqrt{5})}}{2}, \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \cup \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{2 + \sqrt{2(1 + \sqrt{5})}}{2}\right) \subset B(0)$$

By the same way, we will continue to find basins, i.e. we will find points, trajectories of which consist of two, three, etc. steps. After n th step will fall into the interval (a,b) (marked in light gray).

Consequently, we have obtained a constructive proof of the following lemma.

Lemma 1. Pools of attracting fixed $x'_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2$ mapping points consist of an infinite number of disconnected intervals of the Cantor type.

Let's study the dynamics of the functional $x'_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3)^2$, that is, finding and studying basins: Here also solving the equation $x_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3)^2$ finding fixed points

$$x_3 = 0, \quad x_3 = 1, \quad x_3 = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_2 = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}.$$

For convenience, we introduce the $f_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3^2)$ following $f'_3 = 4x_3(x_3 -$ notation and we have

$2)(x_3 - 1)$. We find out the characters of fixed points (5):

$$|f'_3(0)| = 0 < 1, \quad |f'_3(1)| = 0 < 1, \quad \left|f'_3\left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right)\right| \approx 1.52786 > 1,$$

Fig. 6. The basins of attractors.

Fig. 7. Fixed points.

$$\left|f'_3\left(\frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right)\right| \approx 10.4721 > 1.$$

So, the points $x_3 = 0, x_3 = 1$ are attractive and the points $x_3 = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, x_3 = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}$ are repeller fixed points.

In this mapping, also using the Koenigs–Lamerey diagrams [12, 13], we find basins of $f_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3^2), g(x_3) = x_3$ attracting fixed points. To do this, we draw graphs of the function on one coordinate plane (see Fig. 7).

Let us proceed to the elucidation of the basins of attracting fixed points $x_3 = 0, x_3 = 1$. We start by drawing a horizontal and vertical line that is the largest in absolute value of the coordinates of the intersection of the graphs of functions $f_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3^2), g(x_3) = x_3$. This is the point $\left(\frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right)$. The horizontal line will intersect the graph of the function $f_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3^2)$ at the point $\left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right)$. The vertical line will intersect the graph of the function $g(x_3) = x_3$

the point $\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right)$. Now through the point $\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right)$ let's draw a horizontal line. By graphical analysis of the trajectory of all points located outside the segment $\left[\frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right]$, we deduce that they strive to infinity. This means that the desired basins are in the segment $\left[\frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right]$, i.e., the dynamics of the trajectory of intersect lies inside the rectangle $\left[\frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right] \times \left[\frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right]$. Take the trajectories of the points $\omega(1,2) = \{1\}$ and $\omega(1,31) = \{0\}$ (see Fig. 8), they separate the basins of a fixed point $x_3 = \frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$.

Fig. 8. Cobweb for two points.

Fig. 9. The basins of attractors.

This means that at distance ε to the right of this point, the trajectory tends to the point $x_3 = 1$. At distance ε to the left of this point, the trajectory tends to the point $x_3 = 0$. Let's find almost fixed points for the point $x_2 = \frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}$. Trajectories of these points fall on it after one step. The coordinates of almost fixed points are the boundary points of the basins of a given point. In Fig. 8, we draw a horizontal line through the intersection point of the graphs, i.e., through the point $x_3 = \frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$. This line will intersect the graph of the function $f_3 = x_3^2(2-x_3^2)$ at four points. These are the points

$$a = -\sqrt{\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}}, \quad b = \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad c = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad d = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}}.$$

Hence, the point c is a fixed point, the points a, b, d are almost repeller (the locations of these points are shown in Fig. 9).

According to graphical analysis, it is not difficult to notice that the basin of the point $x_3 = 1$ is the interval (c, d) , i.e., $(c, d) \subset B(1)$. The basin of the point $x_3 = 0$ is the interval (b, c) , i.e., $(b, c) \subset B(0)$. The trajectories of all points located in the interval (a, b) in one step will move to the interval (c, d) . This means that $(a, b) \cup (c, d) \subset B(0)$. Now we draw a horizontal line through the abscissa of the intersection

Fig. 10. Inverse graphical analysis.

point of the graphs $x_3 = 0$. This line intersects the graph $f_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3^2)$ at the following two points

(see Fig. 10): $a_1 = -\sqrt{2}, d_1 = \sqrt{2}$.

The lengths of the obtained intervals (a_1, a) and (d, d_1) are equal and these points are symmetric with respect to the point $x_3 = 0$. The trajectories of all points located inside of these intervals will move into the interval (b, c) , i.e., $(a_1, a) \cup (b, c) \cup (d, d_1) \subset B(0)$. For clarity, visually see the basins in a rectangle $\left[\frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right] \times \left[\frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right]$. The basins of attracting fixed points are divided in two colors (Fig. 11): the basin of the point $x_3 = 0$ is black and the basin of the point $x_3 = 1$ is light grey. As a result, we have

$$\left(\sqrt{2}, -\sqrt{\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}}\right) \cup \left(-\frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \cup \left(\sqrt{\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}}, \sqrt{2}\right) \subset B(0)$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}}, -\frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \cup \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \sqrt{\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}}\right) \subset B(1).$$

Continuing, we will find a set of points, whose trajectories in one step will go into the interval (c, d) (light gray zone). Then, we will find the sets of all points, whose trajectories consist two, three, etc. steps, through the n th step will fall into the interval (c, d) .

Consequently, we constructively proved the following lemma holds.

Lemma 2. Basins of attracting fixed points $x'_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3^2)$ display consist of an infinite number of disconnected Cantor-type intervals.

4. CARTESIAN PRODUCT OF ONE-DIMENSIONAL DYNAMICAL SYSTEMS

In this section, we take the Cartesian product of fixed points x_2 and x_3 . As we found out above, each of them has four fixed points. The component x_2 has the following fixed points

$$x_2 = 0, \quad x_2 = 1, \quad x_2 = \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_2 = \frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2};$$

and the component x_3 has the following fixed points

$$x_3 = 0, \quad x_3 = 1, \quad x_3 = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \quad x_3 = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}.$$

Fig. 11. The basins of attractors.

Fig. 12. Classifications of the basins.

Now let's take the plane x_2Ox_3 and place the points on this coordinate plane and with the Cartesian product of these points we get 16 points

$$\begin{aligned} &(0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1), \left(0, \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(0, \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(1, \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(1, \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \\ &\left(\frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, 0\right), \left(\frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, 1\right), \left(\frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, 0\right), \left(\frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, 1\right), \\ &\left(\frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(\frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(\frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(\frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right); \end{aligned}$$

As noted above, each of the $f_2 = x_2^2(2 - x_2)^2$ and $f_3 = x_3^2(2 - x_3)^2$ functional has 4 fixed points, including two attracting and two repelling. With the Cartesian product of these points,

we get 16 fixed points, the characters of which are determined by the following theorems.

Theorem 1. *With respect to Cartesian product of two fixed points are true the following statements:*

- 1) *if both points are attracting, then the points obtained by the Cartesian product are also attracting;*
- 2) *if one of the points is attractive and the second is repeller (regardless of which one), then the resulting points obtained by the Cartesian product are hyperbolic;*

Fig. 13. Classifications of the basins on H_1 .

- 3) *if both points are repellers, then the resulting points obtained by the Cartesian product are repellers.*

Theorem 2. *With respect to Cartesian product of two components of the composition of two Lotka–Volterra mappings described by equations (3), there exist 16 fixed points. Among them*

- 1) *four attractive fixed points: $(0,0)$, $(0,1)$, $(1,0)$, $(1,1)$;*
- 2) *four repellers fixed points*

$$\left(\frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(\frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(\frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(\frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right);$$

- 3) *and the other 8 fixed points are hyperbolic*

$$\left(0, \frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(0, \frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(1, \frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}\right), \left(1, \frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right);$$

$$\left(\frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}, 0\right), \left(\frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}, 1\right), \left(\frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, 0\right), \left(\frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, 1\right).$$

All what given in the theorems above can be visually seen in phase portrait of the basins of attracting fixed points shown in Fig. 12.

As can be seen from Fig. 12, the entire phase space of the attracting fixed points is divided into four colors, marked with letters: the basin of the point $(1,1)$ is colored dark grey (area D); the basin of the point $(0,0)$ is marked in black (area A); white (area C) marks the basin of the point $(0,1)$; the basin of the point $(1,0)$ is marked in light grey (area B).

Now, if we consider the picture in the entire hyperplane H_1 , including the two-dimensional simplex S^2 , then we get the following consequence.

Corollary 1. *For the composition of two Lotka–Volterra mappings described by equations (3), we obtain 16 fixed points:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{\sqrt{-5}}{5}, \frac{3-\sqrt{-5}}{2}, \frac{-1-\sqrt{-5}}{2} \right), \left(0, \frac{3-\sqrt{-5}}{2}, \frac{-1+\sqrt{-5}}{2} \right), \left(0, \frac{3+\sqrt{-5}}{2}, \frac{-1-\sqrt{-5}}{2} \right), \\ & \left(\frac{\sqrt{-5}}{5}, \frac{3+\sqrt{-5}}{2}, \frac{-1+\sqrt{-5}}{2} \right), \end{aligned}$$

1) *four attractive fixed points*
 $(1,0,0), (0,1,0), (0,0,1), (-1,1,1);$

2) *four repellers fixed points*

,

;

3) *and the other 8 are hyperbolic fixed points*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, 0, \frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2} \right), \left(\frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}, 0, \frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right), \left(\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}, 1, \frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2} \right), \left(\frac{1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, 1, \frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right) \\ & ; \\ & \left(\frac{-1+\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}, 0 \right), \left(\frac{-3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{3-\sqrt{5}}{2}, 1 \right), \left(\frac{-1-\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, 0 \right), \left(-\frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, \frac{3+\sqrt{5}}{2}, 1 \right) \\ & . \end{aligned}$$

The phase portrait in the entire hyperplane is shown in Fig. 13. The phase portrait shown in Fig. 12 is a projection of the phase portrait shown in Fig. 13.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

Nowadays, the theory of one-dimensional dynamical systems is an essential part of the theory of dynamical systems. Nonlinear dynamics is an effective tool in the study of various nonlinear processes [14, 15]. The simplicity of the phase space made it possible to find out relatively quickly the patterns characterizing the behavior of the trajectories. Therefore, now one-dimensional dynamics is a well-developed theory that contains deep results and effective criteria. One-dimensional dynamics is accompanied by a simple and visual computer experiment. Based on this, we decided to use this theory of one-dimensional dynamics to study the dynamics of the composition of two Lotka–Volterra mappings.

The relevance of the research of the article is accompanied by the fact that the composition of two Lotka–Volterra mappings can be used to model epidemiological situations. In particular, this theory can be used in studying the dynamics of viral diseases transmitted by direct contact with patients who have concomitant diseases.

The coexistence of two or more diseases that coincide in time or are pathogenetically interrelated in one patient is called comorbidity. This condition modifies the usual clinical picture of these diseases. In most cases, in the presence of combined conditions associated, for example, with HIV infection, the human immunodeficiency virus plays a leading role in pathogenesis. Concomitant diseases also often induce immune disorders themselves. So, the development of HIV infection against their background often exacerbates its course, causing the development of resistance to antiretroviral therapy [16].

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